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Flexible voltage controller and tuning method for robust operation of standalone grid forming converters[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The grid forming inverter plays a key role in standalone power systems, where it must generate a stable and stiff voltage for the elements connected to the grid. One of the most common control structures to achieve the voltage source behavior is the cascaded voltage–current controller in synchronous reference frame. However, conventional tuning strategies do not ensure a robust performance of the voltage controller when delays and bandwidth separation are not negligible. To solve this problem, this work proposes a design and optimization methodology based on bilinear matrix inequalities optimization. This approach ensures the robustness of the voltage control on a wide operational range, while meeting different constraints, such as the bandwidth or the decay rate of the system response. The proposed methodology is not limited to conventional control structures, based on decoupled PI regulators and feedforward terms on each of the axes of the synchronous reference frame. Instead, additional terms or degrees of freedom can be added to boost the performance without increasing the tuning complexity. Simulations show that the proposed controller, along with the tuning methodology, can enhance system robustness with minimal impact on the dynamic response.

1. Introduction

In recent years, grid forming inverters (GFMI) have emerged as a promising solution to enhance the reliability and stability of power grids. These devices, which exhibit voltage-source behavior, are demonstrating their effectiveness in stabilizing power grids, specially as traditional synchronous generators are replaced by inverter-based resources [1].

Beyond their role in grid-connected systems, GFMI are essential for standalone applications, where stable voltage source is critical to support load demands. Standalone applications of GFMI span through various domains, including remote off-grid systems, backup or emergency power solutions, and heavy transportation [2,3]. Additionally, emerging applications, such as port electrification (Shore-to-Ship) is also relying on GFMI to feed loads [4]. In any case, these systems benefit from the voltage regulation capability of GFMI, allowing for a reliable power supply in areas where conventional grid connection is unavailable or it is decoupled through power electronics.

The typical control structure of a GFMI is a cascaded controller composed of two layers [5]. The outer controller, composed of active and reactive power regulators, is only required in grid-connected operation. These controllers will provide the angular

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Table 1
Comparison of inner voltage control structures in GFMI.

	Voltage tracking	Damping	Grid sensitivity	Stability margin	Current limitation	Complexity
Direct voltage synthesis [8]	Poor	Poor	Low	Limited by low damping	No	Low
Single voltage controller [9,10]	Good	Poor	High	Limited by low damping	No	Medium
Cascaded voltage-current controller [11,12]	Good	Good	High	Constrained by cascaded structure	Yes	High

Table 2
Review of tuning and control structure modifications for inner voltage control in GFMI.

Ref.	Approach	Limitation
[17]	Analytical reduction of feedforward gains	Limited to classical PI structure; robustness and dynamic response not addressed
[20]	Parameter optimization for minimum damping	Same as above; focused on stability
[18,19]	Sensitivity-based iterative tuning	Limited to classical PI structure; convergence not guaranteed
[21]	H_∞ robust control	Limited degrees of freedom to tune the controller
[22]	Virtual admittance voltage controller	Improves stability but weakens voltage regulation
[23]	High-pass filtering in feedback path	Enhances damping, but restricts current limitation
[24]	Adaptive voltage control	Requires some time to adjust to varying conditions
[25]	State-feedback control	Abandons conventional PI structure; harder to optimize and implement
[26]	Sliding mode control	Stability analysis is challenging due to non-linearity

frequency and amplitude setpoint of the equivalent voltage source, synchronizing the inverter with the grid and ensuring power sharing capability. Depending on their active power regulator, GFMI are classified into droop-based, virtual machine-based or non-linear oscillators [6]. The inner controller is required in both grid-connected and standalone operation. It ensures that voltage setpoints are met at the point of common coupling between the inverter and the grid or connected loads. Inner controllers must provide proper voltage tracking capability and robust operation. In this context, several strategies can be found in literature [7].

A summary of the main inner control structures is given in Table 1. The simplest inner controller consists on applying the voltage setpoint at inverter terminals [8]. However, this approach falls short in ensuring a precise voltage regulation, because it is an open loop control which does not compensate the voltage drop in the filter stage of the GFMI. A single voltage regulator is a simple approach to ensure the voltage regulation [9]. However, this scheme has shown some limitations, such as insufficient stability margin, constrained bandwidth and sensitivity to parameter variation [10]. Using a cascaded voltage-current controller can overcome previous issues, damping filter resonance and enhancing stability [11,12]. Moreover, the current controller can prevent overloading conditions under contingencies, as it has control over the current flowing through the inverter [13]. The cascaded voltage-current controller of GFMI is a well known structure, which can be developed both in stationary reference frame ($\alpha\beta$) or synchronous reference frame (dq) [14,15]. The latter provides a simpler approach, as sinusoidal signals are turned into DC signals when its reference frame is properly synchronized, enabling the use of classical PI regulators. Apart from PI regulators, dq -based controllers also rely on decoupling and feedforward terms to enhance dynamics. The decoupling terms will minimize the interaction between d and q axes of the control, whereas the feedforward terms can decouple the dynamics of the filter from the grid/load.

Recent works have shed light on the impact of the non-ideal behavior of current and voltage controllers, which impact the classical tuning methodologies of these controllers. These phenomena are specially critical as grid impedance increases or when the bandwidth separation between cascaded controllers is limited, e.g., high power applications with limited switching frequency [16]. Authors in [17] have emphasized the need to reduce feedforward terms and increase the proportional term of voltage regulators to ensure the stability of these controllers. Alternative tuning methodologies have also been suggested to ensure the robustness and the required performance metrics of cascaded controllers: iterative-approaches based on sensitivity analysis [18,19], optimization algorithms [20] and robust control strategies (H_∞) [21], among others.

In the same line, modifications over the classical PI-based control structures have also been proposed, aiming to improve the performance of the controller in terms of robustness and error tracking capability. Replacing the voltage controller with a virtual admittance approach boosts the robustness, at the cost of a reduced regulation capability [22]. In [23], filtering stages were added on some feedback signals. Authors in [24] propose adaptive auto-tuning techniques. State-feedback control [25] and non-linear controllers, such as sliding mode control, have also been proposed for improving the performance under non-linear loads [26]. A summary of the tuning strategies and modified control structures, together with their limitations, is gathered in Table 2.

The main goal of this work is to develop a tuning methodology for robust voltage control of GFMI under standalone operation. For this purpose, a Bilinear Matrix Inequality (BMI) optimization approach is proposed [27,28]. The tuning methodology is applied to the voltage regulator of the cascaded controller, which is particularly susceptible to non-ideal behavior of the current regulator, decoupling and feedforward terms. The proposed methodology can increase its robustness, reduce its overshoot and achieve fast perturbation attenuation in the operation range of the power converter. As the proposed approach is not limited to classical control structures, additional degrees of freedom can be added. In this context, authors evaluate a modified voltage controller which includes different proportional gains for setpoint and feedback voltages, and cross coupled terms in PI and feedforward gains. The proposed methodology enables the addition of degrees of freedom without increasing the tuning complexity.

Fig. 1. Simplified one-line diagram of a GFMI in standalone mode.

The structure of this work is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the problem statement, describing the standalone operation of a GFMI, its control structure and modeling approach in the dq frame. It also outlines the conventional tuning approach for the cascaded voltage-current controller and presents a motivation example demonstrating its limitations in achieving robust performance. Section 3 describes the proposed tuning methodology. Using matrix notation, a generic voltage controller with additional degrees of freedom is defined. Then, by extending the matrix notation to the full model, the required mathematical formulation for applying the BMI optimization is achieved. Once the BMI optimization formulation is presented, a numerical procedure for solving it is also provided. In Section 4, the proposed methodology is applied to the motivational example. The proposed methodology and the voltage control structure with additional degrees of freedom can achieve robust performance across a wide operational range without compromising system dynamics. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the key findings and conclusions.

2. Problem statement

Fig. 1 shows the simplified one-line diagram of a GFMI feeding a standalone system. The typical energy source for the GFMI is an energy storage system, e.g., a battery. This work neglects the dynamics of the energy source and its associated electronics, and an ideal DC voltage source is considered. The power electronic hardware is connected to the loads through an LC filter in order to meet power quality requirements. The filter is composed of an inductor L_c (with its associated resistance R_c) and a capacitor C_f . The loads connected to the inverter are represented through an equivalent load, including a resistive term R_L and inductive term L_L .

The figure also shows a simplified scheme of a dq cascaded voltage-current controller. The voltage controller manages the voltage at load terminals, v_o , whereas the inner current regulator handles the current of the converter i_c . The outer control layer, composed of the active and the reactive power regulators, is not considered. These are usually much slower than inner controllers, and they are not required to operate in standalone operation. The voltage-current controller structure will be explained more into detail into next subsections.

2.1. System modeling

Since the controller is implemented in the dq reference frame, both the controller and the plant are represented according to this reference frame. The controller and plant diagram are represented in Fig. 2. To make the representation more compact, the figure uses complex notation, where $x_{dq} = x_d + jx_q$. All the signals and parameters in the model are represented in per unit notation (pu), except for the base angular frequency ω_b , in rad/s. Using pu normalization removes the dependence of voltage and power ratings and simplifies the analysis. The symbol s is used to represent Laplace variable.

2.1.1. Plant

The plant is composed of the LC filter and the equivalent RL load. The dynamics of the converter current, i_{cdq} , the voltage at the point of connection, v_{odq} , and the load current i_{Ldq} are determined by the application of Kirchhoff's laws in the proposed reference frame, leading to

$$v_{cd} - v_{od} = \frac{L_c}{\omega_b} \frac{di_{cd}}{dt} + R_c i_{cd} - \omega_r L_c i_{cq}, \tag{1a}$$

Fig. 2. Controller and plant diagram in dq frame.

$$v_{cq} - v_{oq} = \frac{L_c}{\omega_b} \frac{d i_{cq}}{dt} + R_c i_{cq} + \omega_r L_c i_{cd}, \tag{1b}$$

$$i_{cd} - i_{Ld} = \frac{C_f}{\omega_b} \frac{d v_{od}}{dt} - \omega_r C_f v_{oq}, \tag{1c}$$

$$i_{cq} - i_{Lq} = \frac{C_f}{\omega_b} \frac{d v_{oq}}{dt} + \omega_r C_f v_{od}, \tag{1d}$$

$$v_{od} = \frac{L_L}{\omega_b} \frac{d i_{Ld}}{dt} + R_L i_{Ld} - \omega_r L_L i_{Lq}, \tag{1e}$$

$$v_{oq} = \frac{L_L}{\omega_b} \frac{d i_{Lq}}{dt} + R_L i_{Lq} + \omega_r L_L i_{Ld}, \tag{1f}$$

where v_{cdq} is the converter output voltage and ω_r is the angular frequency of the inverter. This angular frequency is approximated to 1 pu along this work.

2.1.2. Conventional control equations

The cascaded voltage-current controller includes a v_{odq} voltage regulator in series with a i_{cdq} current regulator. The main goal of the voltage controller is to track desired reference v_{odq}^* at connection point. Its output is a current setpoint i_{cdq}^* , that will be tracked by the current regulator. The current regulator outputs the converter voltage setpoint v_{cdq}^* , which will be applied to the modulator.

Both voltage and current controllers share the same structure: a PI with decoupling and feedforward terms. The decoupling terms aim to decouple the interaction between the d and q axis. Feedforward terms, on the other hand, decouple the inverter from varying load conditions. The voltage regulator will use the load current as feedforward, whereas the current regulator will use the capacitor voltage.

The dynamic equations of the inner current controller and outer voltage regulator are given by

$$v_{cd}^* = k_{pc}(i_{cd}^* - i_{cd}) + k_{ic} \int (i_{cd}^* - i_{cd}) dt - \omega_r L_c i_{cq} + v_{od}, \tag{2a}$$

$$v_{cq}^* = k_{pc}(i_{cq}^* - i_{cq}) + k_{ic} \int (i_{cq}^* - i_{cq}) dt + \omega_r L_c i_{cd} + v_{oq}, \tag{2b}$$

$$i_{cd}^* = k_{pv}(v_{od}^* - v_{od}) + k_{iv} \int (v_{od}^* - v_{od}) dt - \omega_r C_f v_{oq} + i_{Ld}, \tag{2c}$$

$$i_{cq}^* = k_{pv}(v_{oq}^* - v_{oq}) + k_{iv} \int (v_{oq}^* - v_{oq}) dt + \omega_r C_f v_{od} + i_{Lq}, \tag{2d}$$

where k_p and k_i are the proportional and integral gains for the PI regulators (note that the same gain is used for both d and q axis), while subindex v and c are used to identify voltage and current regulator parameters. The controller model also includes the voltage noise input, v_{odq}^δ , which will be considered in the following sections.

To account for non-ideal behavior, the controller model includes discretization and the PWM effects, which are represented as a pure delay. This delay will modify the converter output voltage according to

$$v_{cdq} = v_{cdq}^* e^{-T_D s}, \tag{3}$$

where T_D is the overall delay. If the control sampling period of the converter, T_s , is the same as the PWM period, the overall delay can be approximated to $T_D = 3/2T_s$ (one period for the discretization and half a period for the PWM).

2.2. Conventional voltage-current controller tuning

The most common approach to tune the current controller is to neglect the impact of delays ($T_D = 0$ s). Under these conditions, the decoupling and feedforward terms are ideal and the current loop dynamics can be simplified to Fig. 3. The closed-loop dynamics

Fig. 3. Simplified current loop under perfect decoupling and feedforward.

from reference to actual current is given by

$$\frac{i_{cdq}}{i_{cdq}^*} = \frac{\frac{k_{pc}s+k_{ic}}{s} \frac{1}{(L_c/\omega_b)s+R_c}}{1 + \frac{k_{pc}s+k_{ic}}{s} \frac{1}{(L_c/\omega_b)s+R_c}} = \frac{k_{pc}s + k_{ic}}{(L_c/\omega_b)s^2 + (R_c + k_{pc})s + k_{ic}}. \tag{4}$$

By tuning

$$k_{pc} = \frac{L_c/\omega_b}{\tau_c}, \quad k_{ic} = \frac{R_c}{\tau_c}, \tag{5}$$

following the modulus optimum approach, the dominant pole and the zero are canceled, and the closed-loop dynamics are determined by a first-order system with a time constant τ_c , i.e., (4) reduces to

$$\frac{i_{cdq}}{i_{cdq}^*} = \frac{1}{\tau_c s + 1}. \tag{6}$$

The bandwidth of the current controller, that is given by $\frac{1}{2\pi\tau_c}$ Hz, is usually selected a decade below the switching frequency.

The simplified block diagram to tune the voltage controller is given in Fig. 4. According to the previous explanation, the inner current controller is modeled as an ideal first order system. The decoupling and feedforward terms are considered ideal, even if they are affected by current dynamics.

The ideal closed-loop dynamics for the voltage controller can be expressed as

$$\frac{v_{cdq}}{v_{cdq}^*} = \frac{\omega_b(k_{pv}s + k_{iv})}{C_f \tau_c s^3 + C_f s^2 + \omega_b k_{pv} s + \omega_b k_{iv}}, \tag{7}$$

being a third order transfer function. In this case, the modulus optimum approach cannot be used because it results in an open-loop system with two poles at the origin (unstable). Instead, symmetrical optimum method is a common approach to maximize the phase margin at the crossover frequency [29]. If the proportional and integral gain of the voltage controller are computed as

$$k_{pv} = \frac{C_f}{a\tau_c\omega_b}, \quad k_{iv} = \frac{C_f}{a^3\tau_c^2\omega_b}, \tag{8}$$

the closed loop system is expressed as

$$\frac{v_{cdq}}{v_{cdq}^*} = \frac{1 + a^2\tau_c s}{(1 + a\tau_c s)(a^2\tau_c^2 s^2 + (a-1)a\tau_c s + 1)} = \frac{\frac{1}{a^2\tau_c^2}(1 + a^2\tau_c s)}{(1 + a\tau_c s) \left(s^2 + \underbrace{(a-1)}_{2\xi} \underbrace{\frac{1}{a\tau_c}}_{\omega_n} s + \frac{1}{a^2\tau_c^2} \right)}, \tag{9}$$

where a is a coefficient which is directly related to the damping of the closed-loop poles ξ and phase margin Φ_m [17,30]. The relationship is given by

$$a = 2\xi + 1 = \sqrt{\frac{-1 - \sin \Phi_m}{-1 + \sin \Phi_m}}, \tag{10}$$

where a is usually selected to ensure a phase margin between 36 and 61 degrees, leading to $a \in [1.96, 3.87]$.

The conventional tuning methodology provides a simple approach to tune the gains of the voltage and current PI controllers. However, it assumes ideal dynamics for feedforward and decoupling terms. The current controller is affected by the delay of the discretization and the PWM. On the other hand, the decoupling and feedforward terms of the voltage regulator are limited by the current controller dynamics. If these conditions are neglected, the voltage control performance and robustness can be considerable affected, as it is shown in the following example.

Fig. 4. Simplified voltage loop under perfect decoupling and feedforward.

Table 3

Base values, and inverter and LC filter parameters.

Base values		Inverter		LC filter	
Base power, S_b	1 MVA	Switching frequency, f_{sw}	5 kHz	L_c	0.05 pu
Base voltage, V_b	690 V	Control sampling period, T_s	200 us	R_c	0.006 pu
Base frequency, ω_b	2π50 rad/s	DC bus voltage	1100 V	C_f	0.045 pu

Table 4

Voltage and current regulator parameters.

	Current controller	Voltage controller
Proportional gain, $k_{pc/v}$	0.49	0.125
Integral gain, $k_{ic/v}$	0.18	24.5

Table 5

Loading conditions for evaluating the performance of the standalone GFMI.

Scenario	Load resistance R_L (pu)	Load inductance L_L (pu)	Load impedance $ Z_L = \sqrt{R_L^2 + (\omega L_L)^2}$ (pu)	Inductance to resistance ratio L_L/R_L
#1	1	0	1	10 ⁻⁴
#2	0.819	0.573	1	0.7
#3	8.19	5.73	10	0.7
#4	10	0	10	10 ⁻⁴

2.3. Motivation example

To assess the impact of non-ideal feedforward and decoupling terms on the performance of the GFMI inverter, simulations are conducted using MATLAB/Simulink. The simulation model is based on the diagram presented in Fig. 1. Since the primary objective is to evaluate the dynamics of the current and voltage regulators, switching frequency effects are neglected by using an averaged model. The base values, along with the inverter and LC filter parameters used in the simulation, are summarized in Table 3.

According to the conventional tuning methodology in Section 2.2, the current controller bandwidth is set to 500 Hz, one decade below switching frequency. The voltage controller is tuned to ensure a phase margin of 61°, according to the symmetrical optimum approach. Current and voltage regulator gains are gathered in Table 4.

In standalone operation, the GFMI is expected to operate under different loading conditions, which are determined by the values of R_L and L_L . Four different scenarios are defined for these parameters in Table 5. The table also includes the overall impedance module $|Z_L|$ and the L_L/R_L ratio. In the first two scenarios, the GFMI operates at inverter rated current. For an operating voltage of 1 pu, this is achieved under an impedance module of 1 pu. The inductance to resistance ratio changes from a value close to 0 (purely resistive) to 0.7 (resistive-inductive load). In the third and fourth scenario, the GFMI operates in low loading conditions, to 10% of inverter rated current ($Z_L = 10$ pu).

Fig. 5(a) shows the response of the current controller for d and q axes under a unitary current setpoint step in the d axis. The figure includes the current dynamics for the loading conditions defined in Table 5. For the sake of comparison, the ideal first order response is also included. This first order response would be achieved when the delay is null ($T_D = 0$ s).

The current dynamics in scenario #1 are the closest to the ideal ones. Hence, when the inverter operates under high loading with a resistive load, the impact of the delays can be neglected. However, as the inductive term is increased or the loading is decreased, the response is deteriorated. The current response overshoots as the inductance to resistance ratio is increased (#2), whereas the

Fig. 5. Controller response assuming ideal response and full model.

bandwidth is reduced as the loading decreases (#3 and #4). The coupling between axes due to non-ideal performance of decoupling terms is also visible, as the q axis current is modified under a perturbation in the d axis.

The response of the voltage controller for the d and q axes under a unitary step in the d axis is shown in Fig. 5(b). As in the previous case, the ideal response of the voltage controller is included for comparison. This response would be achieved assuming ideal feedforward and decoupling effects. The real bandwidth and damping of the voltage dynamics is considerably reduced compared to the expected response. The performance of the voltage regulator is deteriorated as the loading increases.

Previous analysis indicates that the performance of the voltage regulator is significantly impacted by non-ideal feedforward and decoupling terms, while the current regulator is also affected to a lesser extent. This work explores whether it is possible to enhance the voltage controller response while retaining the conventional design of the current controller.

3. Proposed approach

To address the problems derived from the presence of delays and non ideal decoupling and feedforward terms, we propose a voltage controller structure which can increase the degrees of freedom of the controller. Then we model the controlled system eliminating the hypothesis of perfect decoupling and feedforward terms by including the delays. With the complete model of the system, that allows us to consider the real inner current controller performance and its impact on the outer voltage controller, we set the control goals to be achieved and quantify them through several control metrics. With this, we propose an advanced controller design technique to guarantee the desired performance levels and maximum robustness by proposing a multi-objective optimization approach through Linear Matrix Inequalities. The methodology of the proposed approach is summarized in the flowchart in Fig. 6.

3.1. Proposed voltage controller

The voltage controller proposed in this work reads as follows

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{cd}^* \\ i_{cq}^* \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{pv}^{dd} & k_{pv}^{dq} \\ k_{pv}^{qd} & k_{pv}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{pv}^*} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od}^* \\ v_{oq}^* \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{pv}^{dd} & k_{pv}^{dq} \\ k_{pv}^{qd} & k_{pv}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{pv}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} \\ v_{oq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{iv}^{dd} & k_{iv}^{dq} \\ k_{iv}^{qd} & k_{iv}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{iv}} \begin{bmatrix} \int (v_{od}^* - v_{od}) dt \\ \int (v_{oq}^* - v_{oq}) dt \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{ff}^{dd} & k_{ff}^{dq} \\ k_{ff}^{qd} & k_{ff}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{ff}} \begin{bmatrix} i_{Ld} \\ i_{Lq} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

This structure keeps the proportional and integral terms as well as the feedforward and decoupling terms of the conventional dq voltage controller. However, additional terms or degrees of freedom are added to boost its performance:

Fig. 6. Methodology followed for the proposed extended voltage controller.

- Different direct gains in each axis (denoted with superindices dd and qq).
- Cross-coupled proportional and integral gains (denoted with superindices dq , qd). Cross-coupled proportional gains, k_{pv}^{dq} and k_{pv}^{qd} , are equivalent to the classic decoupling terms of voltage controllers, but they are not fixed to $\omega_r C_f$.
- Weighting factors for the voltage references, that can be seen with the use of different values for gains applied to the setpoint (k_{pv}^*) and feedback (k_{pv}) signals.
- Feedforward gains k_{ff} (including crossed terms) that allow modifying the way measured currents i_{Ldq} are used to correct its impact. These gains do not have a unitary gain as in the classical approach.

While conventional voltage regulators only require tuning 2 parameters (k_{pv} , k_{iv}), the proposed controller allows tuning up to 16 parameters through the values in matrices K_{pv}^* , K_{pv} , K_{iv} and K_{ff} . However, the proposed controller will not increase the practical tuning effort. The BMI-based optimization will directly compute these gains according to the specified targets. In fact, the conventional PI regulator is recovered as a particular case of this framework when the controller matrix gains structure

$$K_{pv}^* = k_{pv} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad K_{pv} = \begin{bmatrix} -k_{pv} & -\omega_r C_f \\ \omega_r C_f & -k_{pv} \end{bmatrix}, \quad K_{iv} = k_{iv} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad K_{ff} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

is met.

The inclusion of additional degrees of freedom in the proposed voltage controller (11) is key to achieve practical improvements and robustness that are limited with conventional PI-based structures. In classical designs, proportional and integral actions are

identical across axes, and feedforward or decoupling terms are fixed based on ideal assumptions. For instance, crossed terms in reference weighting and integral gain of feedforward are fixed to zero (see (12)). This limits the controller’s ability to shape closed-loop dynamics under load variations or other uncertainties (as delays). By enabling these new controller tunable gains, the proposed controller expands the feasible design space, allowing a multiobjective optimization problem facing the existing trade-off between tracking performance, robustness to disturbances and modeling errors or measurement noise amplification, among other issues.

3.2. Controller tuning targets

The following goals are defined for the design of the voltage controller:

- Low oscillatory behavior. This is related to the robustness against modeling errors and time-varying parameters in the load. The peak of the magnitude of the frequency response of the sensitivity function S is used to quantify this goal. The sensitivity function is the transfer function that models the dynamic behavior from reference to tracking error when there is no reference weighting. In this case, we cannot use that definition, so we apply the alternative one instead: the transfer function that models the dynamics from controlled output noise v_o^δ (drawn in Fig. 2) to the measured output $y_S = v_o + v_o^\delta$ under null voltage references, $v_o^* = 0$. Due to the multivariable nature of the closed loop system, the H_∞ norm is used to quantify the worst case scenario, denoted as $H_\infty^{S^1}$.
- Low overshoot under reference changes: The peak of the magnitude of the frequency response of the complementary sensitivity function T is used to quantify this goal. The complementary sensitivity function is the transfer function that models the dynamic behavior from reference v_o^* to the resulting output voltage $y_T = v_o$. With the same argument, the H_∞ norm is used to quantify the worst case scenario, denoted by H_∞^T .
- Fast voltage tracking capability. This goal is quantified through the closed loop bandwidth. It will also avoid coupling dynamics between the voltage controller and an outer loop (for example, an active and reactive power droop controllers) in grid-connected applications.
- Fast disturbance attenuation: The real part of the dominant poles in closed loop quantifies this goal. It will be called decay rate of the system, denoted by λ .
- Limitation of measurement noise amplification. Assuring a low amplification of the high frequencies inherent to the voltage and current measurements due to the switching nature and high frequency measurement noises. We quantify this amplification with the absolute value of the gains of the controller.
- Robust performance along the possible scenarios. All the previous goals must be fulfilled for all the possible loads assumed in the system. This goal will be addressed by assuring the previous indices along all the possible families of models that define the dynamics.

3.3. System closed-loop modeling

In this section we obtain the state–space model with the proposed controller, when the delay is considered and the assumptions of perfect decoupling are eliminated, allowing us to develop an accurate design strategy.

In order to obtain the full system model, we first present the converter, filter and load equations in state space leading to

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_{cd} \\ i_{cq} \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -\omega_b R_c / L_c & \omega_r \omega_b \\ -\omega_r \omega_b & -\omega_b R_c / L_c \end{bmatrix}}_{A_{i_c}} \begin{bmatrix} i_{cd} \\ i_{cq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \omega_b / L_c & 0 \\ 0 & \omega_b / L_c \end{bmatrix}}_{B_{i_c}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{cd} \\ v_{cq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -\omega_b / L_c & 0 \\ 0 & -\omega_b / L_c \end{bmatrix}}_{-B_{i_c}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} \\ v_{oq} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{13a}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} \\ v_{oq} \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega_r \omega_b \\ -\omega_r \omega_b & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{A_{v_o}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} \\ v_{oq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \omega_b / C_f & 0 \\ 0 & \omega_b / C_f \end{bmatrix}}_{B_{v_o}} \begin{bmatrix} i_{cd} \\ i_{cq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -\omega_b / C_f & 0 \\ 0 & -\omega_b / C_f \end{bmatrix}}_{-B_{v_o}} \begin{bmatrix} i_{Ld} \\ i_{Lq} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{13b}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_{Ld} \\ i_{Lq} \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -\omega_b R_L / L_L & \omega_r \omega_b \\ -\omega_r \omega_b & -\omega_b R_L / L_L \end{bmatrix}}_{A_{i_L}} \begin{bmatrix} i_{Ld} \\ i_{Lq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \omega_b / L_L & 0 \\ 0 & \omega_b / L_L \end{bmatrix}}_{B_{i_L}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} \\ v_{oq} \end{bmatrix}. \tag{13c}$$

¹ The H_∞ norm of a stable system $y = G(s)u$ quantifies the worst-case amplification from input to output over all frequencies, and is defined as

$$\|G(s)\|_\infty = \sup_{\omega \in \mathbb{R}} \bar{\sigma}(G(j\omega)),$$

where $\bar{\sigma}(\cdot)$ denotes the maximum singular value. Equivalently, it can be expressed as the induced gain between finite-energy signals,

$$\|G(s)\|_\infty = \sup_{u \neq 0} \frac{\|y\|_2}{\|u\|_2}, \quad y = G(s)u,$$

that is, the maximum possible amplification of the input signal energy into the output signal energy. This definition is independent of the chosen modeling framework, and applies equally to transfer-function and state–space representations.

The model for load current in (13c) can be expressed as an affine function of the varying parameters

$$\theta_1 = \frac{R_L}{L_L}, \quad \theta_2 = \frac{1}{L_L}, \tag{14}$$

as follows:

$$A_{i_L}(\theta_1, \theta_2) = A_{v_o} - \omega_b I \theta_1 + \omega_b I \theta_2, \quad B_{i_L}(\theta_2) = \omega_b I \theta_2. \tag{15}$$

Then, the (conventional) current and proposed voltage controller are expressed as,²

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{cd}^* \\ i_{cq}^* \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{pv}^{dd} & k_{pv}^{dq} \\ k_{pv}^{qd} & k_{pv}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{pv}^*} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od}^* \\ v_{oq}^* \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{pv}^{dd} & k_{pv}^{dq} \\ k_{pv}^{qd} & k_{pv}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{pv}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} + v_{od}^\delta \\ v_{oq} + v_{oq}^\delta \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{iv}^{dd} & k_{iv}^{dq} \\ k_{iv}^{qd} & k_{iv}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{iv}} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{vd} \\ \sigma_{vq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{ff}^{dd} & k_{ff}^{dq} \\ k_{ff}^{qd} & k_{ff}^{qq} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{ff}} \begin{bmatrix} i_{gd} \\ i_{gq} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{16a}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{vd} \\ \sigma_{vq} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{od}^* \\ v_{oq}^* \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} + v_{od}^\delta \\ v_{oq} + v_{oq}^\delta \end{bmatrix}, \tag{16b}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{cd}^* \\ v_{cq}^* \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{pc} & 0 \\ 0 & k_{pc} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{pc}^*} \begin{bmatrix} i_{cd}^* \\ i_{cq}^* \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -k_{pc} & -L_c \omega_r \\ L_c \omega_r & -k_{pc} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{pc}} \begin{bmatrix} i_{cd} \\ i_{cq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} k_{ic} & 0 \\ 0 & k_{ic} \end{bmatrix}}_{K_{ic}} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{cd} \\ \sigma_{cq} \end{bmatrix} + I \begin{bmatrix} v_{od} \\ v_{oq} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{16c}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{cd} \\ \sigma_{cq} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} i_{cd}^* \\ i_{cq}^* \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} i_{cd} \\ i_{cq} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{16d}$$

where i_c^* is the output of the voltage controller that is, in turn, the reference of the current controller. The current controller finally gives as an input v_c^* , the desired voltage at the converter terminals. Note that a measurement noise signal denoted as v_o^δ has been added to the measured voltage when entering the voltage controller in order to evaluate the robustness of the approach. Finally, to include the effect of the controller discretization and the PWM of the inverter, a delay T_D is applied to the converter voltage setpoint. For obtaining the linear model, the delay is linearized using a first order approximation, leading to

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} v_{cd} \\ v_{cq} \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -1/\tau_d & 0 \\ 0 & -1/\tau_d \end{bmatrix}}_{A_{v_c}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{cd} \\ v_{cq} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1/\tau_d & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\tau_d \end{bmatrix}}_{B_{v_c}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{cd}^* \\ v_{cq}^* \end{bmatrix}. \tag{17}$$

After manipulation of the previous model, controller and approximate delay state space equations, we obtain the overall system dynamics with the following extended state

$$\frac{d}{dt} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_v \\ \sigma_c \\ v_c \\ i_c \\ v_o \\ i_L \end{bmatrix}}_x = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -I & 0 \\ K_{iv} & 0 & 0 & -I & K_{pv} & K_{ff} \\ B_{v_c} K_{pc}^* K_{iv} & B_{v_c} K_{ic} & A_{v_c} & B_{v_c} K_{pc} & B_{v_c} (K_{pc}^* K_{pv} + I) & B_{v_c} K_{pc}^* K_{ff} \\ 0 & 0 & B_{i_c} & A_{i_c} & -B_{i_c} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & B_{v_o} & A_{v_o} & -B_{v_o} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & B_{i_L}(\theta_2) & A_{i_L}(\theta_2, \theta_2) \end{bmatrix}}_{A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_v \\ \sigma_c \\ v_c \\ i_c \\ v_o \\ i_L \end{bmatrix}}_x + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} I \\ K_{pv}^* \\ B_{v_c} K_{pc}^* K_{pv}^* \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{B^*(K)} v_o^* + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -I \\ K_{pv} \\ B_{v_c} K_{pc}^* K_{pv} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{B^\delta(K)} v_o^\delta, \tag{18}$$

that can be written in short as

$$\dot{x} = A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2) x + B^*(K) v_o^* + B^\delta(K) v_o^\delta, \tag{19}$$

with $v_o^* = [v_{od}^* \ v_{oq}^*]^T$ the voltage set-point, $v_o^\delta = [v_{od}^\delta \ v_{oq}^\delta]^T$ the measurement noise associated to the voltage measurement used in the voltage controller, and where K represents the voltage controller gains of the voltage controller to be obtained, i.e., $K = \{K_{pv}^*, K_{pv}, K_{iv}, K_{ff}\}$ (the 16 gains encountered in (11)). Matrix $A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)$ in (19) can be rewritten as

$$A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2) = A_K(K) + A_{\theta_1} \theta_1 + A_{\theta_2} \theta_2, \tag{20}$$

² The integral error dynamics are represented through the variable σ . For instance, one can interpret σ_{vd} as $\sigma_{vd} = \int (v_{od}^* - v_{od}) dt$

with

$$A_K(K) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -I & 0 \\ K_{iv} & 0 & 0 & -I & K_{pv} & K_{ff} \\ B_{v_c} K_{pc}^* K_{iv} & B_{v_c} K_{ic} & A_{v_c} & B_{v_c} K_{pc} & B_{v_c} (K_{pc}^* K_{pv} + I) & B_{v_c} K_{pc}^* K_{ff} \\ 0 & 0 & B_{i_c} & A_{i_c} & -B_{i_c} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & B_{v_o} & A_{v_o} & -B_{v_o} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & A_{v_o} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{21}$$

$$A_{\theta_1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\omega_b I \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_{\theta_2} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \omega_b I & \omega_b I \end{bmatrix}. \tag{22}$$

The load parameters R_L and L_L are unknown, but they are bounded to vary in the box

$$\theta_1 = \frac{R_L}{L_L} \in [\theta_{1,\min}, \theta_{1,\max}], \quad \theta_2 = \frac{1}{L_L} \in [\theta_{2,\min}, \theta_{2,\max}], \tag{23}$$

as specified in Table 5. Since the load conditions are not fixed during the controller design stage and R_L and L_L may vary over time, (18) represents a linear parameter-varying (LPV) system with respect to parameters θ_1 and θ_2 . This affine function of the uncertain parameters enables robust controller design by accounting for parameter uncertainties and ensuring performance across all vertices of the parameter space. Those 4 vertices are defined as follows

$$A_1(K) = A(K, \theta_{1,\min}, \theta_{2,\min}), \tag{24a}$$

$$A_2(K) = A(K, \theta_{1,\min}, \theta_{2,\max}), \tag{24b}$$

$$A_3(K) = A(K, \theta_{1,\max}, \theta_{2,\min}), \tag{24c}$$

$$A_4(K) = A(K, \theta_{1,\max}, \theta_{2,\max}). \tag{24d}$$

The proposed tuning methodology takes advantage of this representation by considering all vertices simultaneously during the optimization process, as detailed in the following sections.

In order to construct the sensitivity function S , one must construct the system that has the measurement noise v_o^δ as input, and the measured controlled output $y_S \equiv v_o + v_o^\delta$ as output. Also, the complementary sensitivity function T must be constructed using the setpoint v_o^* as input and the actual achieved voltage $y_T \equiv v_o$ as output, leading to

$$\text{Sensitivity function } S : \begin{cases} \dot{x} = A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)x + B^\delta(K)v_o^\delta \\ y_S = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & I & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{C_S} x + \underbrace{I}_{D_S} v_o^\delta \end{cases} \tag{25a}$$

$$\text{Complementary function } T : \begin{cases} \dot{x} = A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)x + B^*(K)v_o^* \\ y_T = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & I & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{C_T} x + \underbrace{0}_{D_T} v_o^* \end{cases} \tag{25b}$$

In both functions, state matrix is common (being $A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)$) while input and output matrices are specific for each case, being $B^\delta(K)$, C_S and D_S used for the sensitivity function, and $B^*(K)$, C_T and D_T used for the complementary function.

3.4. Metrics formulation through Linear Matrix Inequalities

In order to state the design procedure, we must first detail how the metrics indicated above can be obtained for the available polytopic model for given controller gains K . The following results allow us to obtain the H_∞ norms of the sensitivity and complementarity functions as well as the decay ratio for the polytopic model describing the system. These metrics formulation are the basis for the design procedure for the proposed controller.

- If there exist symmetric and positive definite matrix P_S and a positive scalar γ_S such that the following linear matrix inequalities are negative definite

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_i(K)^T P_S + P_S A_i(K) + C_S^T C_S & P_S B^\delta(K) + C_S^T D_S \\ B^\delta(K)^T P_S + D_S^T C_S & D_S^T D_S - \gamma_S^2 I \end{bmatrix} < 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \tag{26}$$

then, the H_∞ norm of the sensitivity function S is less than γ_S . To prove this result, assume null references v_o^* and define the Lyapunov function

$$V(t) = x(t)^T P_S x(t), \tag{27}$$

being P a positive definite matrix, and its derivative as

$$\dot{V} = \dot{x}^T P x + x^T P \dot{x}, \tag{28}$$

leading to

$$\dot{V}(t) = (A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)x + B^\delta(K)v_o^\delta)^T P_S x + x^T P_S (A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)x + B^\delta(K)v_o^\delta). \tag{29}$$

As $A(K, \theta_1, \theta_2)$ is a convex function on the parameters, fulfilling (26) in its vertices implies that is fulfilled on its domain. Then, multiply the resulting matrix by $[x^T \ (v_o^\delta)^T]$ on the left and by its transpose on the right. With the definition of the Lyapunov function above, this leads to

$$\dot{V} + y_S^T y_S < \gamma_S^2 (v_o^\delta)^T v_o^\delta. \tag{30}$$

Now, assuming null initial conditions and integrating the previous expression from $t = 0$ to ∞ it leads to

$$\|y_S\|_2^2 < \gamma_S^2 \|v_o^\delta\|_2^2, \tag{31}$$

proving the result.

- If there exist symmetric and positive definite matrix P_T and positive scalar γ_T such that the following linear matrix inequalities are negative definite

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_i(K)^T P_T + P_T A_i(K) + C_T^T C_T & P_T B^*(K) + C_T^T D_T \\ B^*(K)^T P_T + D_T^T C_T & D_T^T D_T - \gamma_T^2 I \end{bmatrix} < 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \tag{32}$$

then, the H_∞ norm of the complementary sensitivity function T is less than γ_T . This result can be proven following the same statements as the previous result but considering the null measurement noises.

- If there exist symmetric and positive definite matrix P_λ and positive scalar λ such that the following linear matrix inequalities are negative definite

$$A_i(K)^T P_\lambda + P_\lambda A_i(K) + 2\lambda P_\lambda < 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \tag{33}$$

then, the system is exponentially stable with a decay rate λ , that is, for any initial condition $x(0)$, the state evolution will satisfy

$$\|x(t)\|_2 < \frac{\lambda_{\max}(P_\lambda)}{\lambda_{\min}(P_\lambda)} \|x(0)\|_2 e^{-\lambda t}, \tag{34}$$

being $\lambda_{\min}(\cdot)$ and $\lambda_{\max}(\cdot)$ the functions that extract the minimum and maximum eigenvalues. This result indicates that $-\lambda$ is the real part of the dominant pole of the system that explains the exponential attenuation of any initial condition caused by disturbances. To prove this result, assume null references and measurement noises and define the Lyapunov function $V(t) = x^T P_\lambda x$. Multiplying matrix in (33) by x^T on the left and x on the right and under the conditions of convexity, that leads to

$$\dot{V}(t) < -2\lambda V(t). \tag{35}$$

This condition is satisfied by (33) due to convexity, as in the previous results. Then, integrate it from $t = 0$ to t leading to

$$V(t) < V(0)e^{-2\lambda t} \tag{36}$$

By means of bounds

$$V(t) > \lambda_{\min}(P_\lambda) \|x(t)\|_2^2, \quad V(0) < \lambda_{\max}(P_\lambda) \|x(0)\|_2^2, \tag{37}$$

the result is finally demonstrated.

3.5. Controller design and numerical procedure

In this work, we search for a controller that assures robustness and performance for the linear parameter time-varying system defined above. To guarantee robustness, low overshoot under step-like voltage reference changes while keeping an appropriate closed-loop bandwidth for rejecting disturbances, we propose to find the controller by means of the following optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{K, \gamma_T, \lambda, P_T, P_\lambda} \quad & \alpha \gamma_T - (1 - \alpha) \lambda \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (26), (32), (33) \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

for some α in $[0, 1]$ weighting factor. With this, we try to minimize the peak of the complementarity sensitivity function γ_T and at the same time to maximize the real part of the closed-loop dominant pole λ . The problem (38) is nonlinear in the controller gains K and Lyapunov matrices P_S, P_T and P_λ , and describes a bilinear matrix inequality (BMI) problem that cannot be handled directly with standard solvers. One approach to handle this situation is the VK procedure that deals iteratively to the problem of obtaining Lyapunov matrices (V stage) and the controller gains (K stage). Although this procedure does not guarantee convergence to the optimal solution in a general situation where the initial solutions are not close to the optimum value, and where all the gain matrices are unbounded, in this case, we are in front of a situation where we can hope near optimal results due to the following facts:

- We have in hand an appropriate initial solution given by the classical control design stated in Section 2.2 through Eqs. (8) and (10);
- Controller gains may be bounded to values that allow limiting the measurement noise amplification;
- Controller gains in (11) and (16a) can be proposed to have a given structure using knowledge from conventional control. For instance, direct d and q terms can be forced to be equal, and crossed dq terms can be forced to be antisymmetric leading to gain matrices

$$K_{pv}^* = \begin{bmatrix} k_{pv}^{dd,qq} & k_{pv}^{dq} \\ -k_{pv}^{dq} & k_{pv}^{dd,qq} \end{bmatrix}, K_{pv} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{pv}^{dd,qq} & k_{pv}^{dq} \\ -k_{pv}^{dq} & k_{pv}^{dd,qq} \end{bmatrix}, K_{iv} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{iv}^{dd,qq} & k_{iv}^{dq} \\ -k_{iv}^{dq} & k_{iv}^{dd,qq} \end{bmatrix}, K_{ff} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{ff}^{dd,qq} & k_{ff}^{dq} \\ -k_{ff}^{dq} & k_{ff}^{dd,qq} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{39}$$

where the original 16 degrees of freedom in (16a) are now reduced to 8 ($k_{pv}^{dd,qq}, k_{pv}^{dq}, k_{pv}^{dd,qq}, k_{pv}^{dq}, k_{iv}^{dd,qq}, k_{iv}^{dq}, k_{iv}^{dd,qq}, k_{iv}^{dq}, k_{ff}^{dd,qq}, k_{ff}^{dq}$) with a given structure.

With these premises we propose the following numerical procedure. At each step j we denote by $K_j, \gamma_{T,j}, P_{T,j}, P_{\lambda,j}$ the actual values for the decision variables.

Step 0: [Classical design] Design the inner current controller gains in (2a)–(2b) by setting a desired bandwidth through setting τ_c and using Eqs. (5). Set a desired phase margin Φ_m for the outer voltage controller defined in (2c)–(2d). Obtain the outer voltage controller gains using Eqs. (8) and (10).

Step 1: [Initialization] Set $j = 1$. Set initially the controller gains K to the ones obtained in Step 0 following the controller structure (2), leading to

$$K_{pv}^* = \begin{bmatrix} k_{pv} & 0 \\ 0 & k_{pv} \end{bmatrix}, K_{pv} = \begin{bmatrix} -k_{pv} & -\omega_r C_f \\ \omega_r C_f & -k_{pv} \end{bmatrix}, K_{iv} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{iv} & 0 \\ 0 & k_{iv} \end{bmatrix}, K_{ff} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{40}$$

and let us call those values K_j .

Step 2: [Actual metrics] Obtain actual H_∞ norms and decay rate with controller K_j through the following set of optimization problems

$$\gamma_{S,j} = \arg \min_{\gamma_S, P_S} \gamma_S, \tag{41a}$$

$$\text{s.t. (26), } K = K_j;$$

$$\gamma_{T,j} = \arg \min_{\gamma_T, P_T} \gamma_T, \tag{41b}$$

$$\text{s.t. (32), } K = K_j;$$

$$\lambda_j = \arg \min_{\lambda, P_\lambda} -\lambda, \tag{41c}$$

$$\text{s.t. (33), } K = K_j.$$

Solving the three optimization problems requires addressing some nonlinearities. For computation of γ_S and γ_T , although these appear as quadratic terms in the optimization formulations (that is, γ_S^2 and γ_T^2 in (26) and (26)), they are treated as the decision variables, which transforms the problem into a linear one, thus simplifying the solution process. On the other hand, the optimization for λ_j is inherently nonlinear due to the presence of the term λP_λ in the LMIs (33), so a line search over λ is proposed to solve it. The solution of these optimization problems define the performance of the actual controller K_j .

Step 3: [V step] With the available controller gains K_j , obtain the Lyapunov matrices $P_{T,j}$ and $P_{\lambda,j}$ through optimization problem

$$P_{T,j} = \arg \min_{t_T, P_T} -t_T, \tag{42a}$$

$$\text{s.t. } \begin{bmatrix} A_i(K_j)^T P_T + P_T A_i(K_j) + C_T^T C_T & P_T B^* + C_T^T D_T \\ B^{*T} P_T + D_T^T C_T & D_T^T D_T - \gamma_T^2 I \end{bmatrix} < -t_T I, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4.$$

$$\gamma_T = \begin{cases} 1.5\gamma_{T,j}, & j = 1 \\ \gamma_{T,j}, & j > 1 \end{cases}$$

$$P_{\lambda,j} = \arg \min_{t_\lambda, P_\lambda} -t_\lambda, \tag{42b}$$

$$\text{s.t. } A_i(K_j)^T P_\lambda + P_\lambda A_i(K_j) + 2\lambda P_\lambda < -t_\lambda I, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4.$$

Fig. 7. Operation bounds for tuning the voltage controller.

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} 0.5\lambda_j, & j = 1 \\ \lambda_j, & j > 1 \end{cases}$$

With this optimization, for given a controller K_j and metrics $\gamma_{T,j}$ and λ_j , we search for the Lyapunov functions that allow us to achieve a gap for a search of new controller gains. The larger the t values, the larger the space for a search of a new controller in the next step. Note that when $j = 1$, the gap is forced at the cost of looking for the Lyapunov functions that achieve worst performance than the initial one (indicated with the $1.5\gamma_{T,j}$ in the H_∞ norm and $0.5\lambda_j$ in the decay). This is done only with the goal of an initial excitation of the algorithm to avoid keeping it frozen on the initial achieved performance, and the values can be changed to other ones that allow the initialization.

Step 4: [K step] Set $j = j + 1$. With the available Lyapunov matrices, obtain the controller that optimizes the following cost index

$$[\gamma_{T,j}, \lambda_j, K_j] = \arg \min_{\gamma_T, \lambda, K} (\alpha \gamma_T - (1 - \alpha) \lambda), \tag{43}$$

s.t. (32), (33), $P_T = P_{T,j-1}$, $P_\lambda = P_{\lambda,j-1}$.

Note: Additional constraints can be applied to limit the search space of K_j in order to limit noise amplification.

Step 5: [Stop criteria] If $|\gamma_{T,j+1} - \gamma_{T,j}| < \epsilon$ and $|\lambda_{j+1} - \lambda_j| < \epsilon$ for some small $\epsilon > 0$ repeat Step 2 to compute the achieved performance and stop. Else, execute Step 2 to 5.

If one wants to achieve a given value for γ_T^* or λ^* , a search over the weighting factor α must be performed.

4. Results

The proposed methodology and voltage controller structure is applied to the motivation example from Section 2.3. Since the current controller remain unchanged, the parameters specified in Table 4 remain valid. To apply the proposed tuning methodology, first, the operation region of the GFMI needs to be bounded. For this work, a region which includes the four scenarios from Table 5 is considered. The bounded operation region are represented in Fig. 7, both in the θ_1 - θ_2 domain, which serves as the bounds for the optimization methodology, and in the Z_L - L_L/R_L domain, which offers a clearer understanding of the load’s electrical properties. The studied scenarios are represented as dots in the figure.

For the optimization, an $\alpha = 0.5$ is selected. Once the numerical procedure is applied, the achieved H_∞^T an H_∞^S are 2.38 and 1.99 respectively, whereas the minimum λ is 36.9. The parameters of the modified voltage controller are summarized in Table 6. To ease the comparison, the table also shows the parameters of the original voltage controller, tuned through symmetrical optimum approach. As it is expected, direct terms have the same value for both axes. On the other hand, cross-coupled terms have the same magnitude but opposite sign, which match the behavior of decoupling terms of conventional controllers.

The proposed controller increases the direct terms of the proportional gain matrix for the voltage feedback, K_{pv} , while it removes those terms in the proportional gain matrix applied to the voltage setpoint, K_{pv}^* . Direct terms in the integral gain matrix K_{iv} are also increased, whereas those in the feedforward matrix K_{ff} do not have a unitary gain, and they are slightly reduced to 0.99. The controller includes cross-coupled terms in the K_{pv} matrix. These are directly related to the classical cross-coupling terms of the voltage regulators, and their magnitude directly depends on $\omega_r C_f$. Additional cross-coupled terms are included in K_{pv}^* , K_{iv} and K_{ff} .

The performance metrics of the conventional PI and the proposed controller, evaluated in the four scenarios from the motivation example are summarized in Table 7 (i.e., evaluated for a static model defined by those parameter values). These metrics have already

Table 6
Proposed voltage controller and conventional controller gains.

	Conventional PI	Proposed controller
Proportional gain matrix applied to voltage setpoint, K_{pv}^s	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.125 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.125 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.04 \\ -0.04 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
Proportional gain matrix applied to voltage feedback, K_{pv}	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.125 & -0.045 \\ 0.045 & -0.125 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.22 & -0.045 \\ 0.045 & -0.22 \end{bmatrix}$
Integral gain matrix applied to the voltage error, K_{iv}	$\begin{bmatrix} 24.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 24.5 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 27 & 1.7 \\ -1.7 & 27 \end{bmatrix}$
Current feedforward gain matrix, K_{ff}	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.99 & -0.07 \\ 0.07 & 0.99 \end{bmatrix}$

Table 7
Performance metrics at different operating conditions, including relative variation.

	Scenario #1		Scenario #2		Scenario #3		Scenario #4	
	Conventional	Proposed	Conventional	Proposed	Conventional	Proposed	Conventional	Proposed
H_∞ of complementary sensitivity function, H_∞^T	2.21	1.07 (-51.6%)	2.38	1.19 (-50%)	1.86	1.19 (-36%)	1.94	1.18 (-39.2%)
H_∞ of sensitivity function, H_∞^S	1.87	1.1 (-41.2%)	1.99	1.38 (-30.6%)	1.49	1.09 (-26.9%)	1.56	1.07 (-31.4%)
Decay rate, λ	37	36.9 (-0.3%)	36.9	37 (-0.3%)	36.9	36.9 (0%)	36.9	36.9 (0%)
Bandwidth (Hz)	42.7	30.4 (-28.8%)	42	30.9 (-26.4%)	51.6	33.1 (-35.9%)	51.8	32.9 (-36.5%)

been described in Section 3.2. The H_∞ norm of both sensitivity and complementary functions are considerably reduced for the proposed controller. In the case of H_∞^T , the improvement ranges from 39.2% to 51.6%, depending on the scenario, whereas for H_∞^S the improvement lies between 26.9% and 41.2%. This is translated into a less oscillatory and more robust controller. The increase in the robustness is achieved while keeping a constant decay rate, λ . Keeping λ constant ensures the same settling time for both conventional PI and proposed controller. The former tuning approach provides a higher bandwidth, but it will be highly dependent on the loading conditions (25% variation for the proposed operation range). The proposed controller and tuning can ensure a more stable bandwidth for all operating conditions (10% variation), at the cost of reducing the bandwidth of the controller.

The voltage response of the conventional PI and the proposed controller under different loading scenarios are represented in Fig. 8. These figures show the time response of the voltage components under a unitary voltage setpoint step in d axis. Oscillations are considerably reduced in the axis where the setpoint is applied. As it was already estimated, the settling time is kept unmodified. The proposed controller increases the coupling between d and q axes. However, the improvement achieved over the d axis is prevailing, achieving an overall improvement in the controller.

To summarize, while the conventional controller requires only two parameters, its performance strongly deteriorates under load variation. By contrast, the proposed controller, despite involving more parameters, achieves significant improvements in robustness: the H_∞ norms of sensitivity and complementary sensitivity functions are reduced by nearly 50%, and the decay rate is preserved. These benefits are obtained automatically by the optimization procedure, so the additional degrees of freedom do not increase the tuning complexity from a practical perspective. Instead, they enable performance levels which cannot be achieved by classical PI structure.

5. Conclusions

The conventional tuning of cascaded voltage-current controllers in GFMI does not ensure a robust response, as it neglects the non-ideal decoupling and feedforward effects. This phenomena is aggravated in high power applications, where the bandwidth limitation between controllers and the delays cannot be neglected. To face this issue, this paper proposes a tuning method based on bilinear matrix inequalities optimization. This approach considers the full model dynamics, without the need of assumptions, and it can assure several targets simultaneously.

Another key aspect of this methodology is that it allows extending the controller structure without increasing manual tuning complexity. In this context, this methodology is applied to a voltage controller structure which includes additional degrees of freedom. Although more parameters are introduced, the optimization procedure automatically determines them. The resulting performance improvements, particularly in robustness against load variations, demonstrate that the additional degrees of freedom provide a practically advantage.

Future work will try to extend this tuning methodology to grid-connected applications, evaluating the interaction of cascaded voltage-current controllers with outer active and reactive power regulators.

(a) Scenario #1

(b) Scenario #2

(c) Scenario #3

(d) Scenario #4

Fig. 8. v_{od} and v_{oq} response comparison under a unitary step in v_{od^*} .

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ander Ordoño: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ignacio Peñarrocha-Alós:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Alain Sanchez-Ruiz:** Writing – review & editing. **Francisco Javier Asensio:** Writing – review & editing.

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